

Euscorpium

Occasional Publications in Scorpiology

**A review of scorpiofauna of China:
nomenclatural notes and updated faunistic
catalogue (Arachnida: Scorpiones)**

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Euscorpius

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A review of scorpiofauna of China: nomenclatural notes and updated faunistic catalogue (Arachnida: Scorpiones)

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Summary

Two genera associated with the scorpiofauna of China are reviewed, *Razianus* Farzanpay, 1987 and *Reddyanus* Vachon, 1972. Holotype female of *Razianus xinjianganus* Lourenço et al., 2010 is presumed to be lost, as well as all type material of other Chinese scorpions described before 2020. Comments are given on the species composition of genus *Reddyanus* with a new synonym: *Isometrus (Reddyanus) tibetanus* Lourenço & Zhu, 2008 = *Reddyanus assamensis* (Oates, 1888) **syn. n.** *Reddyanus kanak* Lourenço, 2023 is tentatively considered as a *nomen dubium*. An updated catalogue of scorpiofauna of China is provided, including their type locality and type depository, protonym, synonym(s), misidentification(s), Chinese equivalent name and distribution in China. Several Tibetan *Scorpiops* species will be addressed in a subsequent paper. Finally, a list of errata in the preceding taxonomic papers by the current author is also included.

Introduction

Razianus xinjianganus Lourenço et al., 2010 was described based on merely a holotype female collected by Clas Naumann in April 1971 near the border between Kashgar Prefecture (Xinjiang Province, China) and Tajikistan, embodying the first record of its subordinate genus in China. It also represents the second species of *Razianus*, a genus whose type species, *R. zarudnyi* (Birula, 1903), was originally described from Sistan and Baluchistan Province of Iran, and later reported from Iraq (Tahir et al., 2014). After a recent two-week (4th–18th August 2024) expedition from Wuqia, through Akto, to Kargilik counties, the author's Xinjiang contact was unable to collect any specimens of this species, only to find *Olivierus przewalskii* (Birula, 1897) in these areas. In an attempt to loan the type specimen from the Museum of Hebei University, Baoding, China for redescription, it was discovered that all old scorpions specimens (studied by M.-S. Zhu et al. before 2012) were most likely lost.

An updated catalogue of scorpiofauna of China is provided. During my current review regarding Chinese scorpion taxa, several diagnostic issues pertaining to the original description of *Reddyanus tibetanus* (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008) were discovered, which prompted me to investigate the genus *Reddyanus* Vachon, 1972. Consequently, 35 species are recognized for this genus, alongside the proposal of one new synonym and one new *nomen dubium*.

Methods & Abbreviations

Morphology. Nomenclature follows Tang (2024a). All the original publications of species and records before the June of 2022 can be sourced from the References in Tang (2022b), while those of the subsequent new species can be retrieved from the References herein. Distribution records listed in the catalogue are all derived from the preceding papers and iNaturalist in a unified format (several widely distributed species were not given their detailed localities), considering their importance in the future revision of those taxa. Notations for scorpion occurrence within China: ●, endemic to China; ○, affirmatively recorded in China; ◐, dubiously recorded in China; *, removal suggested. Revised distribution maps are generated in QGIS (ver. 3.32.3) and SimpleMappr (www.simplemappr.net/) for families Buthidae, Pseudochactidae, Hormuridae, and Scorpionidae (Figs. 1–4), while Chaerilidae and Scorpiopidae require further investigation (work in progress). Coordinates were all sourced from published papers, confirmed iNaturalist records, and examined specimens. In QGIS, 'Esri Imagery' was selected as the base layer. Administrative division vector layers were downloaded from GitCode (gitcode.com/open-source-toolkit/3a3f0/overview).

Abbreviations. TL, total length (in mm); PTC, pectinal tooth count; DSC, denticle subrow count of pedipalp chela movable finger; CL/W, length to width ratio of pedipalp chela; MV L/W, length to width ratio of metasomal segment V; L/D,

Figures 1a–b. Maps showing the distribution of Buthidae species in China (except for *Razianus* and *Reddyanus*). **Figure 1a.** *Hottentotta leetzi* (★), *Hottentotta songi* (★); *Isometrus maculatus* (●); *Langxie feti* (▲); *Lychas mucronatus* (■). **Figure 1b.** *Mesobuthus thersites* (▼); *Olivierus longichelus* (+), *Olivierus martensii* (■), and *Olivierus przewalskii* (▲). **Figure 2.** Map showing the distribution of Pseudochactidae, Hormuridae, and Scorpionidae species in China. *Qianxie solegladi* (◆); *Liocheles australasiae* (●), *Tibetiomachus himalayensis* (▲); *Deccanometrus bengalensis* (★). Scale bars = 1000 km.

Figure 3. Map showing the known distribution of *Razianus* spp. based on Tahir et al. (2014) and this study (star: type localities; dots: other localities; smaller white dots: iNaturalist records of *R. zarudnyi*). *R. birulai* (★, ●); *R. farzanpayi* (★, ●); *R. xinjianganus* (red shade, potential area); *R. zarudnyi* (★, ●). The exemplar scorpion is *R. zarudnyi* (photo courtesy of K. Kaftarbaz).

length to depth ratio; SAT, subaculear tubercle of telson; HT, holotype. Notations will be omitted from the table captions.

Specimen Depositories. CASC (California Academy of Sciences, San Francisco, California, USA); CZRC (Central Zone Regional Centre - Zoological Survey of India, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh, India); FKCP (František Kovařík, private collection, Prague, Czech Republic); MHB (Museum of Hebei University, Baoding, China); MNHN (Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France); MWHU (Museum of Wuhan University, Wuhan, China); NHMUK (Natural History Museum, London, UK); NHRS (Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet, Stockholm, Sweden); NMPC (National Museum of Natural History, Prague, Czech Republic); NZSI (National Collection, Zoological Survey of India, Calcutta, India); USTC (University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei, China); UZMD (Universitets Zoologiske Museet, Copenhagen, Denmark); VT (personal collection of Victoria Tang, Shanghai, China; will in future be donated to NHMUK); ZISP (Zoological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg, Russia); ZMHB (Museum für Naturkunde der Humboldt-Universität, Berlin, Germany).

Scorpion types deposited in MHB

According to their respective original descriptions, type material of the following Chinese scorpions are supposedly deposited in MHB (in chronological and alphabetical order): *Chaerilus tessellatus* Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005, *Hottentotta songi* (Lourenço, Qi & Zhu, 2005), *Scorpiops atomatus* Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005, *Scorpiops langxian* Zhu, Qi & Lourenço, 2005, *Scorpiops luridus* Zhu, Lourenço & Qi, 2005, *Scorpiops shidian* (Zhu, Qi & Lourenço, 2005), *Scorpiops vachoni* (Zhu, Qi & Lourenço, 2005),

Scorpiops yangi (Zhu, Zhang & Lourenço, 2007), *Chaerilus conchiformis* Zhu, Han & Lourenço, 2008, *Reddyanus tibetanus* (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008), *Chaerilus mainlingensis* Di & Zhu, 2009, *Scorpiops lhasa* Di & Zhu, 2009, *Olivierus bolensis* (Sun, Zhu & Lourenço, 2010) (= *O. longichelus*), *Olivierus longichelus* (Sun & Zhu, 2010), *Razianus xinjianganus* Lourenço, Sun & Zhu, 2010, *Scorpiops xui* (Sun & Zhu, 2010), *Olivierus karshius* (Sun & Sun, 2011) (= *O. longichelus*), *Scorpiops lii* (Di & Qiao, 2020), *Scorpiops songi* Di & Qiao, 2020, *Scorpiops lourencoi* Lv & Di, 2022, *Scorpiops rufus* Lv & Di, 2023, and *Scorpiops zhui* Lv, Lourenço & Di, 2023. However, according to Prof. Zhang from Hebei University, China, all old material (before 2012; i.e., until *O. karshius*) have undergone several informal transfers, and their current location is unclear. The disappearance of those types was also confirmed by another anonymous (by request) personnel from Hebei University, who had reorganized the entire specimen chamber of MHB without discovering any scorpion specimens.

The validity of the following species described before 2012 is confirmed without ambiguity: *Scorpiops atomatus*, *Scorpiops luridus*, *Scorpiops shidian*, *Scorpiops vachoni*, *Scorpiops yangi*, *Chaerilus conchiformis*, *Scorpiops lhasa*, *Olivierus longichelus*, and *Scorpiops xui*. Further investigation based on topotypes and molecular analyses is required for: *Chaerilus tessellatus*, *Hottentotta songi*, *Scorpiops langxian*, *Chaerilus mainlingensis*, and *Razianus xinjianganus*. Other species have been and will be (in this paper) synonymized: *Reddyanus tibetanus*, *Olivierus bolensis*, and *Olivierus karshius*. In any case, neotypes must be designated for the above species, or they will have to be degraded to *nomina dubia*.

Systematics

Buthidae C. L. Koch, 1837***Razianus* Farzanpay, 1987**

(Figure 3)

COMMENTS. *Razianus zarudnyi* underwent several nomenclatural and taxonomic changes. It was initially classified under *Hemibuthus* Pocock, 1900 and later transferred to *Buthus* Leach, 1815, leading to its status as a homonym with *Buthus zarudnyi* Birula, 1900 (now transferred to *Sassanidotus* Farzanpay, 1987). *Buthus zarudnianus* Birula, 1905 was therefore erected as a replacement name (Birula, 1905a: 450), accompanied with additional information of several new specimens collected from towns of Ahvaz and Dezful, Khuzestan Province, Iran (Birula, 1905b: 144–145). Lourenço (1996: 94) established a new genus, *Neohemibuthus*, to accommodate *N. kinzelbachi* from Dezful and Masjed-e Soleyman, but did not offer any comparison with *B. zarudnianus*. This species was subsequently synonymized with *B. zarudnianus* by Fet (1997: 66), who introduced a new combination, *Neohemibuthus zarudnyi*, given its distinction from *Buthus*. As noted by Fet (*op. cit.*), Farzanpay (1988: 40) listed a new genus, *Razianus*, to include *Hemibuthus zarudnyi* Birula, 1903 as the type species, stating that it was to be described in a collaboration with Max Vachon. However, this genus was already erected in a neglected work written in Farsi by Farzanpay (1987), named after the Razi Vaccine and Serum Research Institute of Iran. Consequently, *N. zarudnyi* was latterly allocated to *Razianus*.

Apart from *R. zarudnyi* and *R. xinjianganus*, Tahir et al. (2014) subsequently described *R. birulai* Tahir, Navidpour & Prendini, 2014 and *R. farzanpayi* Tahir, Navidpour & Prendini, 2014 from Pakistan, as well as providing a redescription for *R. zarudnyi*. It was discovered that *R. zarudnyi* occupies an extensive area along the Zagros Mountain range on the southwest (Tahir et al., *op. cit.*: fig. 1). All those three species inhabit rocky desert associated with mountainous areas, consistent with the lapidicolous ecomorphotype. According to the diagnostic keys given by Tahir et al. (*op. cit.*: 4), several morphological characters could facilitate the interspecific differentiation of *Razianus*: (1) total length; (2) coloration; (3) ratiometrics of pedipalp chela manus, and metasoma I and V; (4) intercarinal granulation density; (5) development of carapace centromedian carinae and pedipalp chela manus carinae; (6) dorsal edge of adult male pedipalp chela movable finger, sublinear or with proximal lobe (and the degree thereof if present); (7) setation of leg basitarsi and telotarsi; (8) presence/absence of small proximal denticles on cheliceral fixed finger; (9) sexual dimorphism in overall ratiometrics.

The genus *Razianus* can be confidently separated from several other genera occurring in Iran, namely *Androctonus* Ehrenberg, 1828, *Anomalobuthus* Kraepelin, 1900, *Apistobuthus* Finnegan, 1932, *Buthacus* Birula, 1908, *Compsobuthus* Vachon, 1949, *Hottentotta* Birula, 1908, *Iranobuthus* Kovařík, 1997, *Kraepelinia* Vachon,

1974, *Liobuthus* Birula, 1898, *Mesobuthus* Vachon, 1950, *Odontobuthus* Vachon, 1950, *Olivierus* Farzanpay, 1987, *Orthochirus* Karsch, 1891, *Polisius* Fet et al., 2001, *Sassanidotus*, and *Vachoniolus* Levy et al., 1973, by a composite of features: (1) small size (ca. 20–30 mm); (2) dense granulation and weakly to moderately developed mesosomal carinae; (3) metasomal carinae without multiple pronouncedly enlarged denticles; (4) pedipalp with fingers of moderate length, chela incrassate and somewhat cubic, patella short and proximally wide; (5) median ocelli located in the anterior half; (6) movable finger with 7–9 denticle subrows; (7) pectines with 12–17 (♂) and 10–13 (♀) shorter, wider teeth; (8) telson with vesicle bulbous and aculeus elongate, lateral profile of vesicle shows a sharp transition to the aculeus curvature posteriorly (with a moderately developed tubercle at the start point near the ventral side). The small, robust overall habitus links it in particular with genera *Kraepelinia* and *Mesobuthus*, but can be readily differed from the former by character 3 (vs. ventrolateral carinae with enlarged denticles) and the latter by character 6 (vs. 11–12).

***Razianus xinjianganus* Lourenço, Sun & Zhu, 2010**

(Figure 3)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:467E2322-0AFB-4C84-A7D9-3540720178D4>

TYPE MATERIAL. **China, Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region**, Kashgar (or Kaxgar) Prefecture, near Tajikistan, April 1971, holotype ♀, leg. C. Naumann; MHBU (lost, a neotype should be designated as per Yanega et al. (2018) once this species is rediscovered).

AFFINITIES. The following comparison with two Xinjiang buthids is based on the original description and the assumption that it is a valid species since the type is lost. This part is included to facilitate future investigators in rediscovering this species.

Although *R. xinjianganus* can be distinguished by its small adult size (ca. 20 mm in ♀), confusion may still arise for the inexperienced when attempting to differentiate it from the juveniles of *Mesobuthus thersites* (C. L. Koch, 1839) (adult size: 32 mm in ♂ to 60 mm in ♀; Kovařík et al., 2022: 139) and *Olivierus przewalskii* (adult size: 44–53 mm in ♂ and 49–63 mm in ♀) based on the overall habitus. *Razianus xinjianganus* is similar to *M. thersites* in its robust chela (vs. slender in, particularly the juvenile, *O. przewalskii*), and to *O. przewalskii* in its slender metasoma and finely granulated metasomal carinae (vs. robust and strongly dentate in, particularly the adult, *M. thersites*). A single meristic, PTC, serves as the most convenient diagnostic feature for differentiating females: 17–23 in *M. thersites*, 16–20 in *O. przewalskii*, and 12 in *R. xinjianganus*. Female *R. xinjianganus* is well separated from the other two buthids. Another, albeit less convenient, meristic feature is the number of pedipalp movable finger denticle subrows, which ranges from 11–12 in *M. thersites* and 9–11 in *O. przewalskii*, whereas *R. xinjianganus* has only 7–8 rows.

DISTRIBUTION (Fig. 3). China (Xinjiang: Kashgar Prefecture). The exact location of this species in Xinjiang cannot be determined. Based on the known distribution pattern of its congeners which indicates the incapability of trans-mountain dispersal of this genus (Tahir et al., 2014: fig. 1), the Pamir Mountain range may also act as an insurmountable physical barrier that confines the distribution of *R. xinjianganus* to the east, in the west end of the Tarim Basin of Xinjiang.

Reddyanus Vachon, 1972
(Figure 4, Table 1)

COMMENTS. The genus *Reddyanus* Vachon, 1972 is distributed from East Asia (Tibet Autonomous Region, China), South Asia, Southeast Asia and Oceania, with most of which found in India (9 spp. records), Sri Lanka (6 spp. records), Malaysia (5 spp. records), Indonesia (4 spp. records) and Vietnam (4 spp. records). One species, *R. deharvengi* (Lourenço & Duhem, 2010), is included in the IUCN Red List (Tang, 2022b: 17). This genus was initially described as a subgenus of *Isometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828, differentiated by the positions of trichobothria and pedipalp finger dentitions (Vachon, 1972, 1982). Kovařík et al. (2016: 54, 56) elevated it to the genus level based on their disparities in tarsal setation and hemispermatophore structure. This taxonomic decision was subsequently supported by a molecular analysis in Štundlová et al. (2022). Additional characters often useful in many subordinate taxa of the two genera include the relative ratio of pedipalp chela (typically more robust in *Reddyanus* but slender with proportionally longer fingers in *Isometrus*, at least in males) and the shape of subaculear tubercle of telson (typically rhomboid in *Reddyanus* but always triangular in *Isometrus*).

Apart from the 33 species listed in Kovařík & Štáhlavský (2019: 3) and Kovařík et al. (2020: 3), three additional species are hereby added to the genus *Reddyanus*: *R. aareyensis* (Mirza & Sanap, 2010), *R. hainanensis* (Lourenço et al., 2005) and *R. lao* (Lourenço & Leguin, 2012). *Reddyanus aareyensis*, originally classified under the genus *Lychas* C. L. Koch, 1845, was subsequently transferred to its current genus by the first author of its original description after a re-examination upon its leg tibia (lacking tibial spur) and trichobothrial pattern of pedipalp manus (Mirza, 2020: 323–324). On the contrary, the latter two species were excluded from this genus in Kovařík & Štáhlavský (2019: 3). As summarized in Tang (2022b), *R. hainanensis* was once synonymized with *R. petrzekai* (Kovařík, 2003) by Kovařík & Ojanguren (2013: 191), a decision subsequently retracted in Kovařík & Štáhlavský (2019: 3). Current scrutiny of its original description and online photographs (MNHN-RS-RS1175) confirmed its unambiguous placement within *Reddyanus*, although a redescription of this species is warranted. Additionally, the morphometrics of *R. hainanensis* are distinctive in terms of its L/W ratio of metasomal segment V (Table 2). *Reddyanus lao* underwent the same taxonomic changes as that of *R. hainanensis* (Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019: 3). While its

morphometrics are quite similar to those of *R. petrzekai* (Table 2), the original authors did not provide any comparisons, albeit their disjunct geographical distribution.

Reddyanus petrzekai was originally described from Tri An dam, Vietnam, with an additional paratype male from Chanthaburi, Thailand (Kovařík, 2003: 11). This paratype was then ignored in Kovařík & Ojanguren (2013) and other subsequent papers; its geographic location suggests it might be conspecific with, if not representing a new species, either *R. neradi* (Kovařík, 2013) from Namtok Phlio, or *R. schwotti* Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019 from Sa Kao Province. Records of *R. petrzekai* from Sen Monorom (Cambodia) and Tao Island (Thailand) (Kovařík & Ojanguren, 2013: 192) were subsequently revealed to be two new species in their original description, *R. rolciki* Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019 and *R. schwotti* Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019. *Reddyanus deharvengi* is another species found in close proximity to these four species but distinguishes itself by having 10 carinae on metasoma II (vs. 8; Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019: 43). Discarding this doubtful distinction (no verifiable illustration; Lourenço & Duhem, 2010: 635) renders *R. schwotti* highly resemblant of *R. deharvengi*, particularly when comparing the male paratypes of *R. schwotti* from Tao Island (Thailand) and Bokor (Cambodia) with the holotype male of *R. deharvengi*. However, it is beyond my scope to confirm if *R. deharvengi* was erroneously described and whether the two species (or part of the populations) may be conspecific. *Reddyanus petrzekai* was eventually recognized as an endemic species in Vietnam (Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019: 23). Nevertheless, its previous records from Champassak (Laos) and Koh Kong (Cambodia) (Kovařík & Ojanguren, 2013: 192) await reappraisal. Despite *R. petrzekai* being once considered relatively widespread (Kovařík & Ojanguren, 2013: 191), with the subsequent discovery of new species from its previously recorded localities, it appears that *R. lao*, discovered far from the type locality of *R. petrzekai*, may also be heterospecific with this species (Fig. 4). Hence, *R. lao* is also hereby included in this genus as a valid species.

Conversely, the validity of *R. tibetanus* is questionable, a species described upon a single adult male, 38 years following its collection by Kurt Lindberg. The authors distinguished their new species from the geographically proximate *R. assamensis* based on a mere three enigmatic characteristics: (1) pigmentation (paler and weakly maculate in *R. tibetanus*); (2) metasomal carinae and terminal tubercles (“posterior spinoid granules”) of dorsal carinae (weaker in *R. tibetanus*); (3) granulations of carapace and tergites (weaker in *R. tibetanus*). Coloration of specimens is known to be prone to alteration if poorly preserved, with patterns often fading over time. While chronological effect may induce color reduction, the extent to which the color diminishes also hinges on the specific chemical reaction between the specimen and its surroundings (e.g., the composition of preserving fluid and the ambient light of the environment where the specimen jar is stored). The specimen itself also holds several variables: for instance, the time interval between its most recent ecdysis

Figure 4. Map showing the distributions of *Reddyanus* discussed (stars: type localities; dots: other localities; smaller dots: iNaturalist observations identified by the current author). *R. assamensis* (★, ●); *R. deharvengi* (★); *R. hainanensis* (★); *R. lao* (★); *R. neradi* (★); *R. petzkelkai* (★, ●); *R. rolciki* (★, ●); *R. schwotti* (★, ●); *R. tibetanus* (★; *syn. n.* with *R. assamensis*); *R. sp.* (●). White square (□) represents the previous record of *R. petzkelkai* (a paratype male) from Chanthaburi, Thailand that was not subsequently redescribed. White triangles (△) represent the previous records of *R. petzkelkai* from Tatai river, Koh Kong, Cambodia (below; overlapped by a record of *R. schwotti*) and Dong Hua Xao NBCA, Champassak, Laos (above) that were not subsequently redescribed. The exemplar scorpion in the right above is an adult male *R. assamensis* (photo courtesy of F. Kovařík), while that in the left bottom is an adult male *R. petzkelkai* from Vietnam (VT). Abbreviations of Indian states: AS (Assam); CG (Chhattisgarh); MH (Maharashtra); MP (Madhya Pradesh); OR (Odisha); UK (Uttarakhand); UP (Uttar Pradesh); WB (West Bengal).

and fixation in fluids, where freshly moulted individuals are paler. The differences on metasomal segments are indiscernible from their illustrations (cf. Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: figs. 1, 14), and those in granulations should ideally be substantiated by UV photographs which were regrettably absent in the original description. In light of this, I could only extrapolate the credibility of those authors pertaining to their statements on qualitative characters from their other publications. The senior author of *R. tibetanus* had previously described a new *Hottentotta* species, *H. caboverdensis* Lourenço & Ythier, 2006, based on four purported characters, with one of which being “...(iii) more strongly marked granulations on carapace and tergites than in *H. hottentotta* and *H. nigrocarinatus*...” (Lourenço & Ythier, 2006: 72). It is evident, after superimposition, that their figures 2–3 which served to illustrate the interspecific difference of carapacial granulation were reciprocal and based on the same template; i.e., the illustrations for the two species’ carapace were not delineated independently yet modified from one another. This approach, albeit censurable, does not necessarily argue against the authenticity of such difference. However, further inference from the photographs of the holotype of *H. caboverdensis* (MNHN-RS-RS8610) and their juxtaposed species (Kovařík, 2007: fig. 9) deemed the implied assertion that “*H. caboverdensis* possesses a more granulated carapace than *H. hottentotta*” as unjustifiable. Similarly, the two

authors of *R. tibetanus* had also collaborated on a description of a new *Olivierus* species based on the same character (Sun et al., 2010: 36, figs. 2–4), which has been refuted in a recent revision (Tang et al., 2024a: 8–9). On that account, I cannot confidently reckon the similar claim proposed for their new *Reddyanus* cogent. In addition to those untenable qualitative characters, a substantial overlap exists in the meristics of the two species (Table 2; or table 1 in Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 270). The sole potential quantitative difference seems to lie in the chela L/W ratio of the males, where *R. tibetanus* appears to possess a narrower chela. Nevertheless, these data were not derived from a sufficient sample size, rendering it susceptible to variation biases and potential anthropogenic errors introduced during the manual measurement. At first glance, it seems that *R. tibetanus* possesses proportionally shorter and more robust fingers (cf. Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: figs. 3, 16). However, recent observations on iNaturalist revealed an intraspecific variation of *R. assamensis* pertaining to this aspect, based on specimens from India and Bangladesh (cf. obs. IDs = 190419156, 187339396), with the Indian specimen apparently matching *R. tibetanus*. Finally, as an important diagnostic character for this genus, the telson morphology (including the shape of subaculear tubercle, curvature of aculeus, and ratio of vesicle) also displayed no observable distinction between the males of two species (cf. Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: figs. 7, 20). Given the non-opposing and non-discrete nature of the three

Diagnostic characters	<i>R. hainanensis</i>	<i>R. lao</i>	<i>R. petrzekai</i>	<i>R. tibetanus</i>	<i>R. assamensis</i>
TL (♂/♀)	58.8 / 38.4	40.7 (45?) / 37.7 (41.2?)	45–58 (HT = 47) / 37.1	42.7 / -	36–44.6 / 28–35.4
PTC (♂/♀)	15–15 / 14–14	14–14 / 12–13	13–16 / 13	16–16 / -	13–16 / 13–15
DSC	7?	6	6	7?	7?
CL/W (♂/♀)	4 / 4.111	3.944 / 3.882	4.105 (HT) / 4.125 (AT)	5.545 / -	5 / 5.5
MV L/W (♂/♀)	6.538 / 3.857	4.571 / 3.692	4.933 (HT) / 3 (AT)	5.083 / -	5 / 3.615
Telson L/D (♂/♀)	3.6 / 3	3.071 / 2.69	- / -	3.666 / -	3.692 / 3.181
SAT	extended and rounded	extended and rounded	extended and rounded	reserved and triangular*	reserved and triangular*
Sample size	1♂ 1♀	1♂ 1♀	3♂ 1♀	1♂	11♂ 13♀; 5♂ (juv.)
Distribution	China (Hainan)	Laos	Vietnam	China (Tibet)	Bangladesh; India; Nepal
Sources of data	Lourenço, Qi & Zhu, 2005	Lourenço & Leguin, 2012	Kovařík, 2003 Kovařík & Šťáhlavský, 2019	Lourenço & Zhu, 2008	Lourenço & Zhu, 2008 Bangladesh: Kovařík, 2003

Table 1. Morphometric comparisons between discussed *Reddyanus* species. Ratiometrics are all calculated from the tables in the source papers (retention method: truncation). For TL of *R. assamensis*, the maximums were taken from Lourenço & Zhu (2008: table 1). The variation range they gave (♂36–40, ♀28–32) in their revised diagnosis probably did not include the telson length, so the minimums would be higher. The ratiometrics for this species only include the data of the two specimens from Nepal they examined. For *R. lao*, the TL of the holotype male and paratype female were given as 45 and 37 in their diagnosis, which respectively shifted to 40.7 and 37.7 in their table 1. They did not indicate the exclusion of telson length, and further adding those values would render 45 and 41.2, respectively. The telson length was not directly given for *R. assamensis*, *R. hainanensis* and *R. tibetanus*, and is therefore obtained by subtraction using other given values. Telson depth is unknown for *R. petrzekai*. *Both *R. assamensis* and *R. tibetanus* were described as having “strong and rhomboid” SAT in males, but their illustrations (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: figs. 7, 20) appeared that those are relatively weak comparing to the congeners (e.g., cf. *R. hainanensis*; Lourenço, Qi & Zhu, 2005: fig. 8). As a result, for differentiation purpose, the description of this structure is modified as above.

diagnostic characters proposed for *R. tibetanus*, an inevitable conclusion is that it embodies a junior subjective synonym of *R. assamensis*. The holotype of *R. tibetanus* was unable to be examined in this study as it is lost.

Concerning all three species, *R. assamensis*, *R. tibetanus* and *R. hainanensis*, the authors asserted that there were seven subrows of denticles on their pedipalp movable fingers (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 266, 270; Lourenço et al., 2005: 58), a character also employed to distinguish *R. lao* from *R. hainanensis* (Lourenço & Leguin, 2012: 74), where *R. lao* was described as having only six subrows (similarly, they claimed that *R. vittatus* (Pocock, 1900) had seven subrows). This contradicts prior knowledge of this genus, in which all species were considered with six subrows. The finger dentition of other *Reddyanus* species clearly accords with the following pattern (cf. Kovařík & Šťáhlavský, 2019: fig. 29; Lowe & Fet, 2024: fig. 175): six subrows of denticles on the cutting edge of movable fingers (apical row excluded) with the first five subrows flanked proximally by an internal accessory denticle (IAD) and an external accessory denticle (EAD). The assertion of seven subrows can likely be attributed to an EAD flanking the 6th subrow (the most proximal subrow) midway, inducing the illusion of a 7th subrow separated from the 6th subrow by this EAD. The subrows of denticles are commonly

identified by the disjunctions between adjacent subrows, eventually rendering them appear either imbricated or non-imbricated depending on how much the posterior subrow extends to the anterior subrow. The subrows anterior to the most proximal subrow are often slightly oblique proximally. Similar instances of confusion in the genus *Olivierus* Farzanpay, 1987 have also been clarified in Tang et al. (2024a: 11–12, 14). In reality, the continuity of the linearity of the 6th subrow is evident for both *R. assamensis* and *R. tibetanus*, even when based on their hand-drawn illustrations (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 266, fig. 13; 268, fig. 26). Although there is a small gap slightly larger than most interdental spacings within the most proximal subrow near the EAD, it did not cause the dislocation that leads to the imbricated configuration in typical subrows, where the posterior subrow lies internal to the anterior one. In fact, if this small gap was the basis for the authors’ claim of seven subrows, then another gap located more proximally in *R. tibetanus* (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: fig. 26), with five denticles between the two gaps, should qualify this species as having eight subrows. Therefore, the presence of seven subrows of denticles does not serve as a defensible basis for distinguishing these taxa from others. However, the illustration for *R. hainanensis* did show a disjunction at this denticle, resulting in an inwardly slanted profile (Lourenço et

al., 2005: 61, fig. 14). Nevertheless, hand-drawn illustrations can be subject to manipulation and may not be entirely reliable. Another plausible explanation is that the finger was accurately illustrated, and the disjunction was caused by the natural wear of the denticles.

More recently, in his revision of *R. heimi* (Vachon, 1976), Lourenço (2023) described a new species based on a 3rd instar juvenile male from the type series of *R. heimi* deposited at Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France. He rejected the taxonomic decision by Kovařík et al. (2016) and retained *Reddyanus* as a subgenus of *Isometrus*, again without proposing any valid justifications (Lourenço, 2023: 32), but instead arbitrarily defining “artificial” and “valid” genera on his own accord. It is arguable that fragmenting one genus into several entities could compromise its taxonomic stability (Mahony et al., 2024). However, as much as any decision to pursue such atomization should be underpinned by a comprehensive, integrative framework supported by robust evidence, criticisms levied against such a course of action must be grounded in objective evaluations to ensure their defensibility. The original description of *R. kanak* conveniently included only a handful of artificial illustrations for the new species (Lourenço, 2023: figs. 8–14), rendering the accuracy of interspecific differentiations doubtful. In the five differential characters he proposed, characters 1 and 5 are indisputably invalid given the immaturity of the holotype. Character 4 is unobservable and can be heavily influenced by the condition of the preserved specimen (note that in Tang et al., 2023: fig. 91, even for the same sex of the same species, the prosoma profile may differ due to distortion). Validity of character 3 remains in question until a thorough investigation is conducted upon the intraspecific variation of trichobothrial positions of both species. The only apparently valid feature lies in character 2. However, the first two features are rather dubious, especially the development of carination which cannot be verified unless photographs of the authentic specimen are provided. Lourenço (2023: 34) stated that “...*un aiguillon un peu plus long et moins recourbé* (a slightly longer and less curved aculeus)...”, a character which may actually represent the common sexual dimorphism in this genus where the aculeus is typically shorter and more curved in males (*op. cit.*: figs. 15–16). The author did not indicate how he identified the sex of the immature specimen, given that the pectinal tooth count, an age-independent meristic often exhibiting sexual dimorphism, is not practical for such differentiation in *Reddyanus*, while all other sexually dimorphic characters (e.g., ratiometrics of metasoma and pedipalps) are only expressed in late instars and adults. Presumably, the relative size of the pectines was leveraged, although it is uncertain if its sexual difference is prominent or reliable at 3rd instar. The mere strong discordance against the diagnostic characters of this genus involves the absence of a subaculear tubercle in his new species (*op. cit.*: fig. 14). Based on my current knowledge, this structure is omnipresent and age-independent across all previous species of *Reddyanus*. Given that no other materials are known for this species and there is not a single photo for the holotype, one cannot reject the likelihood of teratology or

anomaly (as also mentioned by the author: “...*Vachon (1976) écarta l'exemplaire en question comme étant atypique...*” [Vachon (1976) discarded the specimen in question as atypical]). Similar telsonic anomaly has been observed in a male *Lychas* aff. *buchari* by Newton (2007). The malformed telson was featured by a narrowed vesicle and a thickened aculeus with a bifurcated tip, whose subaculear tubercle was diminished. The holotype *R. kanak* was also illustrated with a proportionally thickened aculeus at the basal section. Upon reviewing online photographs of normal immature *Reddyanus* species, it appears that the girth of aculeus is not, if at all, ontogenetically variable. In light of these considerations, I refrain from including *R. kanak* Lourenço, 2023 within this genus, while assuming its status as a *nomen dubium*.

Consequently, 35 species are recognized here for this genus. In comparison with the list of 33 species in Kovařík & Šťáhlavský (2019) and Kovařík et al. (2020): *R. aareyensis*, *R. hainanensis* and *R. lao* are added; *R. tibetanus* is removed and synonymized with *R. assamensis*; *R. kanak* is considered a *nomen dubium* and not included in the count.

Reddyanus assamensis (Oates, 1888)

(Figure 4, Table 1)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:70EA523D-67B3-41CB-892C-D239FA94091C>

Isometrus assamensis Oates, 1888: 250, figs. 5–6; Kraepelin, 1896: 126; Kraepelin, 1899: 67; Pocock, 1900: 48; Kraepelin, 1913: 135–137; Takashima, 1945: 86; Bastawade et al., 2012: 6.

Isometrus (Reddyanus) assamensis: Vachon, 1972: 177; Vachon, 1976: 38; Vachon, 1982: 100; Kovařík, 1994: 202; Kovařík, 1997: 8; Kovařík, 1998a: 36; Kovařík, 1998b: 111; Fet & Lowe, 2000: 151; Kovařík, 2003: 5; Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 265–268; Yang et al., 2013: 2, 5, 7; Kovařík & Ojanguren, 2013: 185.

Isometrus (Reddyanus [sic]) assamensis: Tikader & Bastawade, 1983: 292.

Reddyanus assamensis: Kovařík et al., 2016: 53; Kovařík & Šťáhlavský, 2019: 3; Shrestha & Dörr, 2020: 430–433; Tang, 2022a: 47; Mohapatra et al., 2022: 24, 26; Pandey et al., 2024: 184, 192–193; Mohapatra, 2024: 5.

= *Isometrus (Reddyanus) tibetanus* Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 268–270, figs. 14–26, 32, 33, table 1; Yang et al., 2013: 2, 5; Di et al., 2013: 52, 54; Kovařík & Ojanguren, 2013: 192; Di et al., 2014: 5–6, 13. **Syn. n.**, <http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:B095157B-CD02-4857-A4FF-813BBE88CBB5> TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Xizang Autonomous Region** (Tibet Autonomous Region), “Region of Chesu”; MHB (lost). No coordinates were given for the type locality and the toponym was imprecise and uncommonly used. Based on the map in the original description, the coordinates are hereby approximated as 30°31'N 82°37'E (30.516667N, 82.616667E), in the Drongpa County of Shigatse City.

Reddyanus tibetanus: Kovařík et al., 2016: 53; Kovařík & Šťáhlavský, 2019: 3; Tang, 2022a: 47; Tang, 2022c: 14.

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **India, Assam State**, Dhuburi District, syntypes comprising 1♂ (lectotype) 5♀, leg. O. G. Smart, NHMUK (type series: 1889.7.31.76-77).

OTHER LOCALITIES AND SPECIMEN DEPOSITORY (localities corrected). **Bangladesh, Tangail District**, Madhupur Upazila, Arankhola Union, Jalchatra Bazaar (“Jalchatra Mission”), FKCP (Kovařík, 2003: 5). **India, Madhya Pradesh State**, Kanker Kuyia (“Kanker”), CASC (Kovařík, 2003: 5); **Madhya Pradesh State**, Narsinghpur, Tendukheda-Rehli road, near Nauradehi Wildlife Sanctuary, CZRC (Mohapatra et al., 2022: 26); **Uttar Pradesh State**, Dehra Village (“Dehra Dun”), CASC (Kovařík, 2003: 5); **Uttar Pradesh State**, Kanpur, CASC (Kovařík, 2003: 5); **Uttarakhand State**, northwestern range of Siwalik, Timli, FKCP (Kovařík, 2003: 5); **West Bengal State**, Kolkata (“Calcutta”), FKCP (Kovařík, 2003: 5). **Nepal, Bagmati Province**, Chitwan District, Bharatpur, Narayangadh (“Narayangarh”, “Narayengath”), FKCP & MNHN (Kovařík, 2003: 5; Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 265; Shrestha & Dörr, 2020: 432); **Bagmati Province**, Kathmandu District, Shantinagar (“Satinagarh”), MNHN (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 265); **Bagmati Province**, Kathmandu District, Tarakeshwar, Sangla Village (“Sangara”), MNHN (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 265); **Gandaki Province**, Manang District, Dharapani Village (“Dhara Pani”), MNHN (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 265); **Koshi Province**, Sunsari District, Itahari, Pathiva, MNHN (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 265); **Lumbini Province**, Butwal in Rupandehi District to Tansen in Palpa District (“Butwal-Tansen”), MNHN (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 265); **Lumbini Province**, Rupandehi District, Siddharthanagar (“Bhairawa”), FKCP (Kovařík, 2003: 5; Shrestha & Dörr, 2020: 432). I cannot locate any place corresponding to “Palture” in Nepal (Lourenço & Zhu, 2008: 265).

DISTRIBUTION (Fig. 4). Bangladesh, China (Tibet), India and Nepal.

Anecdotes and erroneous records of scorpions in China

1. An unidentified *Reddyanus* species in China

In recent years, some anecdotal observations of an unidentified *Reddyanus* species (henceforth referred to as *R. sp.*) have been reported from Zhuhai City (Guangdong Province; cf. iNaturalist, obs. ID = 129862242, a juvenile specimen; a photo montage is available in the figure gallery of this paper on ResearchGate). However, despite my friend's efforts to collect this species in May 2023, he was unable to obtain any new specimens. Thus, the following deductions are based solely on anecdotal photographs of this species.

Many phytophilous buthids, such as *Centruroides gracilis* (Latreille, 1804), *Isometrus maculatus* (DeGeer, 1778), *Lychas mucronatus* (Fabricius, 1798), and *L. scutillus* C. L. Koch, 1845, are renowned for their high dispersal capability and adaptability, leading to their widespread distribution in regions with similar climates far beyond their original habitats (Dupré, 2022; Fet & Lowe, 2000; Kovařík, 2019; Trujillo et al.,

2017). Given the potential likelihood of accidental invasion, a comprehensive photographic comparison of *R. sp.* with all previously described species was conducted. Color pattern is a surprisingly useful diagnostic character for certain *Reddyanus* species, utilized herein as the primary criterion for excluding implausible candidates. This approach reduced the number of species for comparison from 34 (excluding *R. hainanensis* and *R. tibetanus*, as discussed earlier) to 18 species, following a thorough examination of available photographs of fresh specimens or *in vivo* habitus. For the two species with only photographs of antiquated specimens available which may suffer from the decay of color patterns, *R. deharvengi* and *R. lao*, they can both be readily differentiated from *R. sp.* by their more curved aculeus and an extended, rounded subaculear tubercle (cf. MNHN-RS-RS1177, MNHN-RS-RS8825, and MNHN-RS-RS8904). Concerning coloration, three of the remaining 16 species display the highest resemblance to *R. sp.*: *R. hofereki* Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019, *R. majkusi* Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019, and *R. zideki* (Kovařík, 1994). However, both *R. majkusi* and *R. zideki* can be distinguished from *R. sp.* by their conspicuously shorter and more bulbous telson (cf. Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019: figs. 208, 214). The telson of *R. hofereki* is also proportionally more bulbous than that of *R. sp.* and is further distinguished by a more rhomboid subaculear tubercle (cf. Kovařík & Štáhlavský, 2019: fig. 205).

Eleven of the 13 remaining species were depicted in (Kovařík & Ojanguren, 2013): *R. bilyi* (Kovařík, 2003), *R. feti* (Kovařík, 2013), *R. heimi*, *R. jendeki* (Kovařík, 2013), *R. krasenskyi* (Kovařík, 1998), *R. kurkai* (Kovařík, 1997), *R. navaiae* (Kovařík, 1998), *R. neradi*, *R. petrzelkai*, *R. problematicus* (Kovařík, 2003) and *R. vittatus* (Pocock, 1900). After obtaining the photographs of these species (courtesy F. Kovařík), it was confirmed that most of them exhibit noticeably distinct color patterns from *R. sp.* Moreover, they can be easily differentiated by chela morphology, metasomal ratios, telson shape, and subaculear tubercle size. The only species that bears a certain level of resemblance is *R. heimi* from New Guinea and Oceania (New Caledonia). While this species shares several similarities with *R. sp.*, such as an analogous overall color pattern, relatively slender pedipalps and metasoma, an elongated telson, and a triangular subaculear tubercle, several features allowed distinguishments. *R. heimi* possesses a shorter and more curved aculeus, and the manus of adult male *R. heimi* is more robust. Additionally, several notable differences in the color pattern are observed: (1) the anterior margin of the carapace in *R. sp.* is infusate, while it matches the base color in *R. heimi*; (2) dark coloration is concentrated at the distal region of the pedipalp patella in *R. sp.* but covers the entire segment in *R. heimi*, forming a reticulate pattern with the proximal region being immaculate; (3) *R. sp.* features six light yellow sections on the posterior margin of the tergites (essentially as a yellow transverse band divided by five longitudinal stripes), while *R. heimi* has only four; (4) dark stripes on the 7th tergites are radial from the posterior margin in *R. sp.*, but showcase a lyre-shaped pattern in *R. heimi*. Based on these distinctive characters, I reject the possibility

that *R. sp.* represents an invasion record of *R. heimi*. The sole available information on *R. corbeti* (Tikader & Bastawade, 1983) is derived from its original description. According to the authors (Tikader & Bastawade, 1983: 305), females exhibit a more elongated metasoma than males, a major character that evidently differentiates this species from *R. sp.*, provided that their sex determination was correct. Moreover, the aculeus was described as “much curved” (*op. cit.*: 310), contradictory to *R. sp.* While the coloration description aligns well with *R. sp.*, the presence of yellow spots and bands on the telson of *R. corbeti* (*op. cit.*: 305) is non-existent in *R. sp.*

As a result, *R. assamensis* was left as the mere option for the possible identity of *R. sp.* This species is the most widespread within its genus, which has been reported from the states of Assam, Chhattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal in India (Pandey et al., 2024: 192). Preliminary comparisons based on the adult male photographs of a live specimen of *R. sp.* and two preserved specimens of *R. assamensis* (including a lectotype; FKCP) revealed no morphological distinction: the color pattern of *R. sp.* matched perfectly with *R. assamensis*, while in terms of the pedipalp chela, metasoma and telson morphology, the two species also appeared to be identical. The only observable difference appeared to be a more conspicuous yellow preocular region along the anteromedian sulcus. Given the widespread distribution and phytophilous nature of *R. assamensis*, the records from Zhuhai may epitomize a case of anthropogenic introduction of this species via timber import, should they fail to represent a new species.

Furthermore, an observation record on iNaturalist suggests the possible existence of an unidentified *Janalychas* species in China, currently known from Tsona City (26°59'08.7"N 93°07'46.5"E) of Shannan City in south Xizang (“Arunachal Pradesh”; cf. iNaturalist, obs. ID = 33791383). The present catalogue, however, excludes this genus record.

2. Historical anecdotes

A Chinese amateur, notorious for illicitly appropriating photographs and videos of scorpions without proper attribution, has now escalated his misconduct by spreading unfounded rumors regarding the scorpiofauna of China across both domestic and international online platforms. This behavior is particularly counterproductive during a phase when much of the Chinese audience remain lacking the foundational knowledge about scorpions, particularly the domestic species, to critically assess the credibility of such anecdotes. Although the current author has never instigated personal animosity towards him despite his reprehensible deeds, this individual has consistently sought to denigrate the author while concealing himself behind a mixed group of amateurs and scholars. This collective ultimately launched a campaign of cyberbullying against the author and her friends (see supplementary file of Tang (2022a)).

In the first instance, this individual referenced two photographs of a large buthid species from a Baidu Tieba (Chinese online platform) post dated 26th July 2014, in which the original poster claimed it to be the “scorpion king” of

Mengyin County, Shandong Province, inexplicitly implying that the specimen was caught in the wild. Upon the current author identifying the specimen as an adult female *Parabuthus granulatus* (Ehrenberg, 1831), and thus exposing the record as fraudulent, the amateur retorted with misplaced confidence, professing that *P. granulatus* had not yet entered the Chinese pet trade at that time, and that the author was “being careless.” This assertion is particularly humorous, as the current author had precisely embarked on her scorpion studies in 2014. An effortless search in Tieba post records swiftly debunked the claim: as early as 26th May 2014, a user noted that juvenile *P. granulatus* specimens were being sold for 900 CNY each; by 30th July 2014—just four days after the post in question—another user was advertising adult *P. granulatus* for 2500 CNY. In reality, there was no need to even verify the species’ availability in 2014 to dismiss the original record as spurious. Anyone with rudimentary analytical skills and basic scorpion taxonomic knowledge could easily identify the absurdity and replicate the hoax by merely covering their pet scorpion in dirt and falsely alleging it to be wild-caught.

The second rumor is even more preposterous. Based on fragmented recollections from local residents and just two photographs (one of which was a screenshot from a video), both depicting a dead, pitch-black scorpion (but not the same), this amateur confidently declared that the scorpion was twice the size of an “ordinary” specimen, reaching 75–80 mm, despite the glaring absence of any reference scale in those photos. He indicated that an undescribed black *Olivierus* species existed in China, further citing an iNaturalist observation of *Olivierus fuscus* (Birula, 1897) identified by the current author. A facile inspection reveals that both specimens were, in fact, artificially darkened *Olivierus martensii* (Karsch, 1879) (Fig. 10). The primary photograph, which the amateur repeatedly brandishes as evidence of a colossal black scorpion native to China, actually originates from a Chinese book titled <My Father Han Fujū> (Fig. 9). The book author cited an explanatory paragraph for the photo (*op. cit.*: 22–23; translated herein from Chinese):

“During the ‘Jinan Massacre’, when the Japanese army occupied southern Shandong, they engaged in widespread slaughter and arson, and the provincial government was also afflicted. A group of Japanese soldiers intruded the garden behind the provincial government building, fishing in the river. Suddenly, two giant scorpions crawled out of the rockery cave with one of which stung a soldier to death. The Japanese soldiers opened fire and killed one, while the other escaped. This is the photo of the dead scorpion. Since then, whenever our children went to play in the garden, they would always feel a bit uneasy, fearing that a giant scorpion might suddenly crawl out.”

The caption accompanying the image purported the scorpion was found in the backyard of a provincial government building and measured 68 centimeters (or “28 inches”)—a clearly circulated error, with the correct measurement most likely being 2.8 inches. A more realistic reconstruction of the scenario at that moment can be hypothesized as follows: A

Supraspecific rank	Total	Endemic	Endemism	Total	Endemic	Endemism
	<i>Untrimmed</i>			<i>Trimmed</i>		
Buthidae	13	5	0.38	12	5	0.42
<i>Hottentotta</i>	2	2	1	2	2	1
<i>Isometrus</i>	1	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Langxie</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1
<i>Lychas</i>	2	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Mesobuthus</i>	1	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Olivierus</i>	3	0	0	3	0	0
<i>Razianus</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1
<i>Reddyanus</i>	2	1	1	2	1	1
Chaerilidae	9	6	0.67	9	6	0.67
<i>Chaerilus</i>	9	6	0.67	9	6	0.67
Pseudochactidae	1	1	1	1	1	1
<i>Qianxie</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1
Scorpiopidae	37	32	0.86	35	32	0.91
<i>Scorpiops</i>	37	32	0.86	35	32	0.91
Hormuridae	2	1	0.5	2	1	0.5
<i>Liocheles</i>	1	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Tibetiomachus</i>	1	1	1	1	1	1
Scorpionidae	1	0	0	1	0	0
<i>Deccanometrus</i>	1	0	0	1	0	0
Scorpiones	63	45	0.71	60	45	0.75

Table 2. Diversity and endemism of Chinese scorpions, indicative of dispersal ability. Trimmed data (reddened) are derived from the removal of several species (see the updated catalogue).

soldier was positioned near the rockery when two *Olivierus martensii* suddenly emerged from the crevices. In the soldier's peripheral vision, the scorpions appeared as swift, dark shadows while his attention was focused elsewhere. Startled, the soldier inadvertently came into physical contact with one of the scorpions (a female) and was stung. His agitation triggered a stress response among the other soldiers, one of whom attempted to shoot the second scorpion. However, due to its, actually, small size, the scorpion succeeded in escaping and concealing itself beneath debris. To dramatize the event, the soldier who was stung suggested dying the scorpion that stung him black and may have exaggerated its size.

Unfortunately, many netizens continued to believe this amateur, who perceived the current author as being an arrogant, self-proclaimed authority in scorpiology. This phenomenon highlights the deficiency in contemporary Chinese education for basic logic, epistemology, and information literacy, which can be detrimental to any fields of study. The current author believes that the advancement of scorpiology necessitates collaborative efforts from both experts and public, underscoring the paramount importance

of establishing a sound epistemological basis. Therefore, decisive actions must be undertaken to effectively counter the fallacious claims propagated by those self-perceived disseminators of scorpiology, whose action may progressively incur entrenched cognitive barriers. Evidence highlighting the pervasively insufficient knowledge pertaining to Chinese scorpiology of the domestic populace has recently been indicated in Tang et al. (2024: 37).

In addition, the widely known Chinese vernacular name “*辽克尔蝎*” (pronounced “*liáo kè ěr*” in Pinyin), which refers to an unspecified scorpion species lacking formal description or illustration, is hereby presumed to be a transliteration of the genus *Liocheles* Sundevall, 1833. This appellation has found extensive usage in Chinese online scientific introductory articles of scorpions, often alongside a plethora of other chaotic or ambiguous scorpion names. Names serve as foundational labels that enable individuals to comprehend and associate concepts or entities; thus, establishing a systematic nomenclature within the scientific context is crucial. Arbitrarily coined common names hinder a proper understanding of scorpions (Tang, 2022a).

- *Scorpiops* ■ *Chaerilus* ■ *Olivierus* ■ *Hottentotta* ■ *Reddyanus* ■ *Langxie* ■ *Razianus*
- *Qianxie* ■ *Tibetiomachus* ■ *Isometrus* ■ *Lychas* ■ *Mesobuthus* ■ *Liocheles* ■ *Deccanometrus*

Figures 5–6. Pie charts depicting trimmed total (5) and endemic (6) species proportion of each genus within scorpions of China. **Figure 7.** Scorpion taxa described from China at five-year intervals (except for the first, second and seventh columns). Junior synonyms are included and represented by the subordinate genera of their respective senior synonyms. **Figure 8.** Cumulative scatterplot showing the increasing trend of scorpion taxa described from China (including junior synonyms) from year 1879 to 2024. Dots represent the year of change

3. Erroneous records reported in the previous papers

As per Tang (2022b: 1), the following species with all their currently confirmed localities beyond China are excluded from the present catalogue: *Hottentotta alticola* (Pocock, 1895) (from Pakistan), *Heterometrus longimanus* (Herbst, 1800) (from Andaman Islands of India, Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines and Singapore), *H. silenus* (Simon, 1884) (from Cambodia, Thailand and Vietnam; misidentified as *H. petersii* (Thorell, 1876) which is limited to Singapore and Malaysia), *Orthochirus scrobiculosus* (Grube, 1873) (from Turkmenistan), and *Scorpiops longimanus* Pocock, 1893 (from Bangladesh and India; retained in Lv & Di (2023: 325)). *Scorpiops hardwickii* (Gervais, 1843) and *S. petersii* Pocock, 1893 are provisionally retained, but they will be officially removed in an upcoming paper within the same journal.

However, there have been anecdotal reports of *H. silenus* from provinces in China bordering Vietnam (e.g., Guangxi). Yet, no verifiable wild populations are confirmed with photographic evidences. This species is a popular pet scorpion in China, and those rare reports might represent escaped individuals that succeeded in temporary survival considering the similar climates between adjacent regions. Curiously, Wang et al. (2019: 77) asserted that they collected “*H. petersii*” from Hainan Province, but without providing any coordinates or photographs in the wild. Their figure 2a showed that the alleged “*H. petersii*” was in fact *H. silenus*.

Chaerilus conchiformis Zhu et al., 2008 was originally misidentified as *C. pictus* (Pocock, 1890) in Qi et al. (2005) from Tibet, a species which was therefore excluded from the previous checklist of the current author. However, Kraepelin (1913: 153) mentioned a male from Dafla Hills (South Xizang) which was not subsequently analyzed. After further reviewing Bastawade (2006: map 1), it is confirmed that both *C. pictus* and its junior synonym, *C. gemmifer* Pocock, 1894, have multiple records from the disputed territory in South Xizang (“Arunachal Pradesh”). Consequently, this species is hereby appended to the scorpiofauna of China. A review of this genus is in progress, and the checklist below includes unpublished, revised information.

Updated catalogue of scorpiofauna of China

Since Di et al. (2014), the composition of scorpiofauna of China was hardly reviewed until Tang (2022b). Several new species and new records have occurred thereafter (Figs. 5–8), as well as some crucial taxonomic changes, which warrants another updated catalogue for the Chinese taxa. Two endemic monotypic genera in China have been established (Tang, 2022b; Tang et al., 2023), *Qianxie* (*Q. solegladi*) and *Langxie* (*L. feti*), with the former already listed in Tang (2022b). Eight new species of *Scorpiops* Peters, 1861 were described: *S. deshpandei* Tang et al., 2024, *S. kovariki* Tang et al., 2024, *S. matthewi* Tang et al., 2024, *S. tongtongi* Tang, 2022, *S. lourencoi* Lv & Di, 2022, *S. reini* Tang, 2024, *S. rufus* Lv & Di, 2023, *S. zhui* Lv et al., 2022 (Tang, 2022d; Lv & Di, 2022b; Lv

et al., 2022). Additionally, the misidentification of *S. kubani* in Yunnan (retained in Lv & Di, 2023: 325) led to another new species, *S. lowei* Tang, 2022 (Tang, 2022e). *Scorpiops bhutanensis* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983 was also formally recorded in China for the first time (Lv & Di, 2022a). More recently, a new species of genus *Hottentotta* Birula, 1908, *H. leetzi* Ythier, 2024 was described from Tibet, apparently representing the highest elevation record of scorpions (4920 m a. s. l.).

In an earlier revision of Xinjiang *Olivierus* (Tang et al., 2024a), only two species of this genus was recognized, *O. longichelus* and *O. przewalskii*, which both appear to occupy an extensive area in that province. *Olivierus bolensis* was confidently synonymized with *O. longichelus*, while *O. karshius* was only tentatively considered synonymous with the same species. However, since the type material are lost, *O. karshius* remains a synonym unless future investigation rediscovered topotypes fully conforming to its original diagnosis.

The catalogue below comprises the currently recognized scorpion taxa in China, alongside their type locality and type depository, protonym, junior synonym(s), misidentification, Chinese equivalent names (for species), and distribution within China. In total, 63 (or 60, after removal) species from 14 genera of 6 families are included.

Buthidae C. L. Koch, 1837

1. Genus *Hottentotta* Birula, 1908

(1) *Hottentotta leetzi* Ythier, 2024

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Xigazê City, Kangmar County, Wāgya La, near the border with Bhutan; MNHN.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 利氏霍屯督蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Xigazê City (Kangmar County: Wāgya La).

(2) *Hottentotta songi* (Lourenço, Qi & Zhu, 2005)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Ngari Prefecture, Burang County, low valley of Kongque He, near the border with Nepal; MHBU (lost).

PROTONYM. *Mesobuthus songi* Lourenço, Qi & Zhu, 2005.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 宋氏霍屯督蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Ngari Prefecture (Burang County: Kongque He).

2. Genus *Isometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828

(1) *Isometrus maculatus* (DeGeer, 1778)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. “**Suriname and Pennsylvania**”; NHRS.

PROTONYM. *Scorpio maculatus* DeGeer, 1778.

SYNONYMS. *Scorpio dentatus* Herbst, 1800; *Buthus (Isometrus) filum* Ehrenberg, 1828; *Tityus aethiops* C. L. Koch, 1844; *Tityus longimanus* C. L. Koch, 1844; *Lychas americanus* C. L. Koch, 1845; *Lychas paraensis* C. L. Koch, 1845; *Scorpio (Lychas) gabonensis* Lucas, 1858; *Scorpio (Lychas)*

Figure 9. Photograph of the purported “giant scorpion (‘巨蝎’)” (adult female *Olivierus martensii*) that was killed after attacking a Japanese soldier, measuring 28 inches (‘二十八英寸’) or 68 centimeters (‘68公分’), on page 23 of the book *<My Father Han Fuju>* (*<我的父亲 韩复榘>*). Scanned from the book by the current author. **Figure 10.** Artificially dyed adult male *Olivierus martensii* by the current author, photoshopped with a rescaled ruler.

guineensis Lucas, 1858; *Lychas mabillianus* Rochebrune, 1884; *Isometrus europaeus quinquefasciatus* Franganillo, 1931; *Isometrus madagassus* Roewer, 1943.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 斑等距蝎 [corrected translation].

DISTRIBUTION (○). Hainan; Taiwan.

3. Genus *Langxie* Tang, Jia, Liu, 2023

(1) *Langxie feti* Tang, Jia, Liu, 2023

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi Prefecture, Zayü County, Golag Township; VT.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 费氏狼蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Zayü County: Cawarong and Golag townships).

4. Genus *Lychas* C. L. Koch, 1845

(1) *Lychas mucronatus* (Fabricius, 1798)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. “**India**” (east); UZMD.

PROTONYM. *Scorpio mucronatus* Fabricius, 1798.

SYNONYMS. *Scorpio (Androctonus) curvidigitatus* Gervais, 1843; *Tityus varius* C. L. Koch, 1844; *Isometrus chinensis* Karsch, 1879 (●); *Isometrus atomarius* Simon, 1884; *Lychas mentaweius* Roewer, 1943; *Lychas baldasseronii* Di Caporiacco, 1947; *Lychas nucifer* Basu, 1964; *Lychas kotao* Lourenço, 2020.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 尖刺信使蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Fujian; Guangxi; Guangzhou; Hainan; Taiwan; Yunnan.

(2) *Lychas scutillus* C. L. Koch, 1845 *

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **Indonesia, Riau Islands**, Bintan Island; NHMUK.

SYNONYMS. *Isometrus weberi* Karsch, 1882; *Isometrus mesor* Simon, 1884; *Isometrus phipsoni* Oates, 1888; *Archisometrus nigrimanus* Kraepelin, 1898.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 纤细信使蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Shanghai (invasion; extinct).

5. Genus *Mesobuthus* Vachon, 1950

(1) *Mesobuthus thersites* (C. L. Koch, 1839)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **Kazakhstan, Qyzylorda Region**, south of Qyzylorda (neotype); NMPC.

PROTONYM. *Androctonus thersites* C. L. Koch, 1839.

SYNONYM. *Buthus eupeus mongolicus* Birula, 1911 (●).

NOMEN NUDUM. *Mesobuthus beijiangensis* Zhang, 2009.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 斗士中杀牛蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Gansu; Inner Mongolia; Ningxia; Xinjiang.

6. Genus *Olivierus* Farzanpay, 1987

(1) *Olivierus longichelus* (Sun & Zhu, 2010)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region**, Bortala Mongol Autonomous Prefecture, 10 km south of Jinghe County; MHBU (lost).

PROTONYM. *Mesobuthus longichelus* Sun & Zhu, 2010.

SYNONYMS. *Mesobuthus bolensis* Sun, Zhu & Lourenço, 2010

(●); *Mesobuthus karshius* Sun & Sun, 2011 (●); *Olivierus tarabaevi* Fet, Kovařík, Gantenbein & Graham, 2021.

MISIDENTIFICATION. *Olivierus intermedius* (Birula, 1897).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 长螯奥氏蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Xinjiang: Bayingolin (Qiemo and Ruoqiang counties), Bortala (Bole City; Jinghe County), Changji (Wujiaqu City), Ili (Ghulja and Korgas counties; Khorgos City), Kashgar (Yarkant and Makit counties), and Tacheng (Shawan City) prefectures; ?Kizilsu Prefecture (Artux City).

(2) *Olivierus martensii* (Karsch, 1879)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. “**Singapore**”; ZMHB.

PROTONYM. *Buthus martensii* Karsch, 1879.

SYNONYM. *Buthus confucius* Simon, 1880 (●).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 马氏奥氏蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Anhui; Beijing; Fujian; Hebei; Henan; Hubei; Inner Mongolia; Jiangsu; Liaoning; Ningxia; Qinghai; Shaanxi; Shandong; Shanxi; Sichuan; Tianjin.

REMARKS. *Buthus martensii hainanensis* Birula, 1904 (●) is presumably a junior synonym of this species (Tang et al., 2024a: 19).

(3) *Olivierus przewalskii* (Birula, 1897)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region**, Bayingolin Mongol Autonomous Prefecture, near Lop Nur Lake and Cherchen Oasis, in the east edge of Tarim Basin; ZISP.

PROTONYM. *Buthus caucasicus przewalskii* Birula, 1897.

NOMEN NUDUM. *Mesobuthus nanjiangensis* Zhang, 2009.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 普氏奥氏蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Gansu: Dunhuang and Jiuquan (Guazhou County) cities; Inner Mongolia: Alxa League (Ejina Banner); Xinjiang: Aksu (Aksu and Kuqa cities), Bayingolin (Bügür, Qiemo, Ruoqiang, and Yuli counties; Korla City), Bortala (Bole City), Ili (Ghulja County), Kashgar (Yarkant and Makit counties), and Kizilsu (Artux City; Wuqia County) prefectures, Turpan (Shanshan and Toksun counties), Tiemenguan, and Tumxuk cities, and Yizhou District (Hami City).

7. Genus *Razianus* Farzanpay, 1987

(1) *Razianus xinjianganus* Lourenço, Sun & Zhu, 2010

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region**, Kashgar Prefecture, near Tajikistan; MHBU (lost).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 新疆拉兹蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xinjiang: Kashgar Prefecture.

8. Genus *Reddyanus* Vachon, 1972

(1) *Reddyanus hainanensis* (Lourenço, Qi & Zhu, 2005)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Hainan Island**, southeast region; MNHN.

PROTONYM. *Isometrus (Reddyanus) hainanensis* Lourenço, Qi & Zhu, 2005.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 海南雷氏蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Hainan (“southeast region”).

(2) *Reddyanus assamensis* (Oates, 1888)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **India, Assam State**, Dhuburi District; NHMUK.

PROTONYM. *Isometrus assamensis* Oates, 1888.

SYNONYM. *Isometrus (Reddyanus) tibetanus* Lourenço & Zhu, 2008 (●). **Syn. n.**

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 阿萨姆雷氏蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Guangdong (?); Zhuhai City (Beikou Village). Xizang: Shigatse City (Drongpa County: “region of Chesu”).

Family **Chaerilidae** Pocock, 1893

1. Genus **Chaerilus** Simon, 1877

(1) *Chaerilus assamensis* Kraepelin, 1913

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **India, Assam State**; NZSI.

SYNONYM. ?*Chaerilus dibangvalleyicus* Bastawade, 2006 (●).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 阿萨姆寇里蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Zayü County); = “Arunachal Pradesh: Dibang Valley District”.

(2) *Chaerilus conchiformis* Zhu, Han & Lourenço, 2008

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bayi District, Bayi Town; MHB (lost).

MISIDENTIFICATION. *Chaerilus pictus* (Pocock, 1890).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 贝壳形寇里蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Bayi District: Baishuwang and Bayi towns; Mainling City: Zhaxiraodeng Township and Milin Town).

(3) *Chaerilus mainlingensis* Di & Zhu, 2009

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mainling City, Milin Town, Gongbuwang Manor; MHB (lost).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 米林寇里蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Mainling City: Gongbuwang Manor in Milin Town).

(4) *Chaerilus pictus* (Pocock, 1890)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **Bangladesh, Sylhet Division**, Sylhet District, Sylhet City; NHMUK.

PROTONYM. *Uromachus pictus* Pocock, 1890.

SYNONYM. *Chaerilus gemmifer* Pocock, 1894 (○).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 着色寇里蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Mêdog County) and Shannan City (Tsona City); = “Arunachal Pradesh”.

(5) *Chaerilus pseudoconchiformis* Yin, Qiu, Pan, Li & Di, 2015

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bayi District; USTC.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 拟贝壳形寇里蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Bayi District).

(6) *Chaerilus tessellatus* Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, Drepung Township; MHB (lost).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 格纹寇里蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Bayi District: Dongjiu Village and Sejila Mountain; Mêdog County: Drepung Township).

(7) *Chaerilus tricostatus* Pocock, 1899

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **India, Assam State**, Tinsukia District, Sadiya Town; NHMUK.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 三肋寇里蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Mêdog and Zayü counties) and Shannan City (Tsona City); = “Arunachal Pradesh: Upper Rottung in Siang District”.

(8) *Chaerilus tryznai* Kovařík, 2000

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bomê County; FKCP.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 忒氏寇里蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Bomê and Mêdog (Hanmi Village) counties).

(9) *Chaerilus wrzecionkoi* Kovařík, 2012

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bomê County, Tongmai Town, 30 km west of “Donjung”; FKCP.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 帷氏寇里蝎 [corrected transliteration].

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Bomê County: Tongmai Town).

Family **Pseudochactidae** Gromov, 1998

1. Genus **Qianxie** Tang, 2022

(1) *Qianxie solegladi* Tang, 2022

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Kunming City, Luquan County, Wumeng Township, Zhongping Village; VT.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 索氏钳蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Sichuan: Liangshan Prefecture, and Panzhihua and Yibin cities; Yunnan: Chuxiong and Kunming cities.

Family **Scorpiopidae** Kraepelin, 1905

1. Genus **Scorpiops** Peters, 1861

(1) *Scorpiops asthenurus* Pocock, 1900

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **India, West Bengal State**, Kalimpong, near Darjeeling; NHMUK.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 弱尾类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Mêdog and Zayü counties) and Shannan City (Tsona City); = “Arunachal Pradesh”.

(2) *Scorpiops atomatus* Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Nang County; MHB (lost).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 黑斑类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi (Nang (Tonga Town) and Zayü (Xiazayü Town) counties) and Shannan (Gyaca County) cities.

(3) *Scorpiops bhutanensis* Tikader & Bastawade, 1983

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **Bhutan, Trashigang District**, Gomchu; NZSI.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 不丹类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Xizang: Shannan City (Tsona City).

(4) *Scorpiops deshbandei* Tang, Ouyang, Liu & Šťáhlavský, 2024

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Mêdog County, Drepung Township; VT.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 德氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Mêdog County: Drepung Township).

(5) *Scorpiops hardwickii* (Gervais, 1843) *

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **Nepal**, Himalayan Mountain Range; NHMUK.

PROTONYM. *Scorpio hardwickii* Gervais, 1843.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 哈氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Xizang: Lhasa City (“Nyenchén Tanglha Mts.”, probably in Damxung County).

REMARKS. This population is most likely conspecific with *S. tibetanus* after examining one adult female (Lowe & Tang, 2024) from the material series in Kovařík (2000: 176). It will be addressed in an upcoming paper.

(6) *Scorpiops ingens* Yin, Qiu, Pan, Li & Di, 2015

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Lhasa City; USTC.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 硕大类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Lhasa City.

(7) *Scorpiops jendeki* Kovařík, 2000

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Nujiang Lisu Autonomous Prefecture, Lushui City, Gaoligongshan National Nature Reserve; FKCP.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 詹氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Baoshan City (Longling County; Longyang District; Tengchong City); Dehong (Lianghe and Longchuan (Wangzishu Township) counties), Dali, and Nujiang (Fugong and Gongshan counties; Lushui City) prefectures.

(8) *Scorpiops kamengensis* (Bastawade, 2006)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **India, Arunachal Pradesh State** (or **China, “Zangnan”**; disputed territory),

West Kameng District, 7 km west of Bomdila, “Sara Village”; NZSI.

PROTONYM. *Euscorpiops kamengensis* Bastawade, 2006.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 卡蒙类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Shannan City (Tsona City); = “Arunachal Pradesh: West Kameng District”.

(9) *Scorpiops kovariki* Tang, Ouyang, Liu & Šťáhlavský, 2024

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Zayü County; VT.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 寇氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Zayü County).

(10) *Scorpiops langxian* Zhu, Qi & Lourenço, 2005

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Nang County; MHB (lost).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 朗县类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi (Nang and Zayü (Xiazayü Town) counties; Bayi District: Baishuwang Town) and Shannan (Gyaca County) cities.

REMARKS. *S. langxian* is presumably a junior synonym of *S. tibetanus* Hirst, 1911 (Tang, 2023: 49).

(11) *Scorpiops leptochirus* Pocock, 1893

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **Bangladesh**, “N. E. Bengal”; NHMUK.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 瘦螯类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Xizang: between Nyingchi City (Mêdog County) and Shannan City (Tsona City); = “Arunachal Pradesh”.

(12) *Scorpiops lhasa* Di & Zhu, 2009

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Lhasa City; MHB (lost).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 拉萨类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Lhasa City.

(13) *Scorpiops lii* (Di & Qiao, 2020)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Shannan City, Lhünzê County; MHB.

PROTONYM. *Euscorpiops lii* Di & Qiao, 2020.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 李氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Shannan City (Lhünzê County).

(14) *Scorpiops lourencoi* Lv & Di, 2022

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Xigazê City; MHB.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 路氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Lhasa (Nyêmo County) and Xigazê (Lhatse County; Samzhubzê District) cities.

REMARKS. New localities with precise coordinates were referenced from iNaturalist observations identified by the current author: 108811752, 156711825 and 229896779. No specific location was given for the type locality.

(15) *Scorpiops lowei* Tang, 2022

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Xishuangbanna Dai Autonomous Prefecture, Menghai County, Menghai Town; VT.

MISIDENTIFICATION. *Scorpiops kubani* (Kovařík, 2004).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 洛氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Xishuangbanna Prefecture (Menghai County: Menghai Town).

(16) *Scorpiops luridus* Zhu, Lourenço & Qi, 2005

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Nang County; MHB (lost).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 浅黄类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Nang County).

(17) *Scorpiops margerisonae* Kovařík, 2000

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**; FKCP.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 玛氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Lhasa (Nyêmo County), Nyingchi (Nang County), and Shannan (Nêdong District) cities.

(18) *Scorpiops matthewi* Tang, Ouyang, Liu & Šťáhlavský, 2024

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Xigazê City, Samzhubzê District; VT.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 迈氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Xigazê City (Samzhubzê District).

(19) *Scorpiops novaki* (Kovařík, 2005)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Nyingchi City, Bomê County; FKCP.

PROTONYM. *Euscorpium novaki* Kovařík, 2005.

SYNONYM. *Euscorpium karschi* Lourenço, Zhu & Qi, 2005 (●).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 诺氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Bomê and Zayü (Xiazayü Town) counties).

(20) *Scorpiops petersii* Pocock, 1893 *

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **India, Himachal Pradesh State**, Shimla; NHMUK.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 佩氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). “Xizang and Xikang (eastern Tibet and western Sichuan of China)”.

REMARKS. The Chinese population is most likely misidentified given the considerable geographic distance from the type locality as well as the presence of an effective physical barrier, the Himalayan Mountain Range, in between.

(21) *Scorpiops puerensis* (Di, Wu, Cao, Xiao & Li, 2010)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Puer City; MWHU.

PROTONYM. *Euscorpium puerensis* Di, Wu, Cao, Xiao & Li, 2010.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 普洱类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Puer City (Lancang County; Simao District).

(22) *Scorpiops reini* Tang, 2024

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Dehong Dai and Jingpo Autonomous Prefecture, Yingjiang County; VT.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 瑞氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Dehong Prefecture (Yingjiang County).

(23) *Scorpiops rufus* Lv & Di, 2023

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Xigazê City; MHB.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 赭类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Xigazê City.

(24) *Scorpiops shidian* (Zhu, Qi & Lourenço, 2005)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Shidian County, Jiucheng Township; MHB (lost).

PROTONYM. *Euscorpium shidian* Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 施甸类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Baoshan City (Shidian (Jiucheng Township; Jingtangba) County; Longyang District).

(25) *Scorpiops songi* Di & Qiao, 2020

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Shannan City, Lhozhag County; MHB.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 宋氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Shannan City (Lhozhag County).

(26) *Scorpiops taxkorgan* Lourenço, 2018

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region**, Kashgar Prefecture, southwest of Tashkorgan Township, “Taxkorgan Natural Reserve”; MNHN.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 塔什库尔干类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xinjiang: Kashgar Prefecture (“Taxkorgan Natural Reserve”).

(27) *Scorpiops tibetanus* Hirst, 1911

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Lhasa City, Qüxü County, Qushui Bridge (“Tsangpo Valley, Chaksam Ferry”); NHMUK.

SYNONYM. *Scorpiops pococki* Zhu, Qi & Lourenço, 2005 (●).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 西藏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Lhasa (Maizhokunggar and Qüxü counties; Chingoinqü District), Nyingchi (Mainling City; Zayü County (Xiazayü Town); Bayi District), Shannan (Gyaca County; Nêdong District), and Xigazê (Samzhubzê District) cities.

REMARKS. Localities include those originally reported for *S. pococki*, require further confirmation. New localities with precise coordinates (from Chingoinqü; also reported in the

original description of *S. pococki*) were referenced from iNaturalist observations identified by the current author: 170567377 and 226468225.

(28) *Scorpiops tongtongi* Tang, 2022

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Dehong Dai and Jingpo Autonomous Prefecture, Yingjiang County, near Tongbiguan Township; VT.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 通氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Dehong Prefecture (Yingjiang County: near Tongbiguan Township, Chashanzhai and Rongshuwang).

(29) *Scorpiops vachoni* (Zhu, Qi & Lourenço, 2005)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Xishuangbanna Dai Autonomous Prefecture, Mengla County; MHBV (lost).

PROTONYM. *Euscorpiops vachoni* Qi, Zhu & Lourenço, 2005.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 瓦氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Xishuangbanna Prefecture (Mengla County: Bujiao and Manlongdai villages).

REMARKS. New locality with precise coordinates (from Manlongdai) was referenced from one iNaturalist observation identified by the current author: 200190520.

(30) *Scorpiops validus* (Di, Cao, Wu & Li, 2010)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Honghe Hani and Yi Autonomous Prefecture; MWHU.

PROTONYM. *Euscorpiops validus* Di, Cao, Wu & Li, 2010.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 强壮类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Honghe Prefecture (Honghe (Mengzi City), Lvchun, and Yuanyang counties).

(31) *Scorpiops vonwicki* Birula, 1913

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **India, Arunachal Pradesh State** (or **China, “Zangnan”**; disputed territory), Abor Hills; ZISP.

PROTONYM. *Scorpiops petersi von-wicki* Birula, 1913.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 韦氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Nyingchi City (Mêdog County); = “Arunachal Pradesh: Abor Hills”.

(32) *Scorpiops wrzecionkoi* Kovařík, 2020

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Shannan City, Nagarzê County, near Sangjian; FKCP.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 帷氏类蝎 [corrected transliteration].

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang: Shannan City (Nagarzê County: near Sangjian).

(33) *Scorpiops xui* (Sun & Zhu, 2010)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Puer City, Menglian County, Lafu Village; MHBV (lost).

PROTONYM. *Euscorpiops xui*.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 徐氏类蝎 Sun & Zhu, 2010.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Puer City (Menglian County: Lafu Village).

(34) *Scorpiops yangi* (Zhu, Zhang & Lourenço, 2007)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Wenshan Zhuang and Miao Autonomous Prefecture, Maguan County, Gulinqing Township; MHBV (lost).

PROTONYM. *Euscorpiops yangi* Zhu, Zhang & Lourenço, 2007.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 杨氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Wenshan Prefecture (Maguan (Gulinqing Township) and Malipo counties).

(35) *Scorpiops zhangshuyuanii* (Ythier, 2019)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Yunnan Province**, Dehong Dai and Jingpo Autonomous Prefecture, Yingjiang County, Tongbiguan Township; MNHN.

PROTONYM. *Euscorpiops zhangshuyuanii* Ythier, 2019.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 张氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Yunnan: Dehong Prefecture (Yingjiang County: Tongbiguan Township); ?Lincang City (Cangyuan Va, Gengma Dai and Va, and Zhenkang (Nansan Town) counties).

REMARKS. Populations recently reported from Lincang City in Tang & Štáhlavský (2024) require further study.

(36) *Scorpiops zhui* Lv, Lourenço & Di, 2023

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Chongqing Province**, Wuxi County, Nongan Village; MHBV.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 朱氏类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Chongqing: Wushan (Zhuxian Town) and Wuxi (Nongan Village; Yintiaoling Nature Reserve (Lanying Grand Canyon)) counties.

(37) *Scorpiops jingshanensis* Li, Wu, Cao & Di, 2016 *nomen nudum*

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. Not explicitly designated; the specimens upon which the name was based were from Huzhaoshan Mts., Jingshan County, Jingzhou City, Hubei Province, China, deposited in MWHU (Ar.-MWHU-HBJS0701–02).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 京山类蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Hubei: Jingshan City (Huzhaoshan).

Hormuridae Laurie, 1896

1. Genus *Liocheles* Sundevall, 1833

(1) *Liocheles australasiae* (Fabricius, 1775)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. “In the islands of the Pacific Ocean” (*in insulis Oceani pacifici*); NHMUK.

PROTONYM. *Scorpio australasiae* Fabricius, 1775.

SYNONYMS. *Ischnurus complanatus* C. L. Koch, 1837; *Scorpio gracilicauda* Guérin Méneville, 1843; *Scorpio (Ischnurus) cumingii* Gervais, 1844; *Chactas brunneus* Bellevoye, 1870; *Ischnurus pistaceus* Simon, 1877; *Hormurus australasiae* var. *γ suspectus* Thorell, 1888; *Buthus brevicaudatus* Rainbow, 1897; *Hormurus australasiae brevidigitatus* Werner, 1936.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 南亚滑螫蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Fujian; Hainan; Hongkong; Taiwan; Yunnan.

2. Genus *Tibetiomachus* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 *nomen dubium*
(1) *Tibetiomachus himalayensis* Lourenço & Qi, 2006 *nomen dubium*

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **China, Tibet Autonomous Region**, Ngari Prefecture, Burang County, Gurla Mandhata; MNHN.

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 喜山藏毒勇蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (●). Xizang; Ngari Prefecture (Burang County; Gurla Mandhata).

REMARKS. *Liocheles nigripes* (Pocock, 1897) is presumably a senior synonym of this species (Tang, 2022c: 2). The original illustration conflicted with its description, which was meant to define the generic diagnosis. Consequently, it was deemed a *nomen dubium* due to the absence of key diagnostic features [ICZN 75.5].

Scorpionidae Latreille, 1802

1. Genus *Deccanometrus* Prendini & Loria, 2020

(1) *Deccanometrus bengalensis* (C. L. Koch, 1841)

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. **India, West Bengal State** (lectotype); ZMHB.

PROTONYM. *Buthus bengalensis* C. L. Koch, 1841.

SYNONYMS. *Heterometrus fastigosus* Couzijn, 1981; *Heterometrus nepalensis* Thorell, 1876; *Heterometrus tibetanus* Lourenço, Qi & Zhu, 2005 (●).

CHINESE EQUIVALENT. 孟加拉德干异距蝎.

DISTRIBUTION (○). Xizang; Ngari Prefecture (Burang County; Kongque He).

List of errata

Below, errors discovered in the preceding taxonomic papers made by the current author are listed, despite the insignificance of most flaws. Notifications are welcomed should readers detect any further errors. They will be subsequently announced in the comments under the publication pages on ResearchGate. The present catalogue also corrected the authorship of the species described in Qi et al. (2005), which may have been incorrectly cited in the preceding papers..

1. Tang (2022b):

(1) Page 3 (right column): "...The generic epithet is a noun in apposition, the *Pingyin* for “钳蝎” (*qián xiē*) in Chinese...", was a type error, which should be "**Pinyin**".

(2) Pages 4 (right column) and 6 (left column): "...25°89'59"N 102°72'47"E...", was actually in decimal format (25.8959°N 102.7247°E), which equals "25°53'45.24"N 102°43'28.92"E" in DMS format; no error for the maps (Tang, 2022b: figs. 60–61).

(3) Page 4: the scale bar of fig. 4 should be **1 mm**.

(4) Page 12 (right column): "...were synapomorphies for *Pseudochactidae*...", was a type error, should be

"**Pseudochactinae**".

(5) In addition, numbers were incorrectly labelled in Tang (2022a: figs. 6–7, 10–11, 19–33). Numbers 6 and 7, as well as 10 and 11, should be switched. Numbers for pedipalp segments should follow a "white-to-UV light" sequence. The description of the species, however, was based on the figure captions.

2. Tang (2022c):

(1) Page 3 (left column): "...the measurement of pedipalp chela by Di et al. (2010) was incorrect...", was a citation error, which should be "**Qi et al. (2005)**".

(2) Page 4: the location labelled for *S. puerensis* in **fig. 2** was incorrect, and a more accurate one has been provided in Tang (2022c: fig. 274).

(3) Page 5 (right column): "...more robust in *O. bolensis*, 2.63 in male and 2.54 in female vs. 2.99 in female of *O. longichelus*...", was a data citation error, which should be "**4.077**", "**4.767**" and "**5.418**" respectively. This error has been corrected in Tang et al. (2024a: 5).

(4) Page 6: "To begin with, in Sun's dissertation (2010: 74)...Later, in Sun & Zhu (2010b) where they described *O. longichelus*", was a chronological error, as the dissertation was written **before** "Sun & Zhu (2010b)". This error has been corrected in Tang et al. (2024a: 8).

*Given the errors and the fact that most issues discussed in this paper have been addressed in the more in-depth subsequent papers, I recommend readers to simply refer to Tang (2023), Tang et al. (2024a) and this paper.

3. Tang (2022e):

(1) Page 21 (right column): "Scorpiops tibetanus Hirst, 1911...note that only *Shigatse* represents the type locality of this species", was incorrect, and the type locality should be "**Qüxü**". This error has been corrected in Tang (2023: 48).

4. Tang et al. (2023):

(1) Pages 3 and 5: "...carapace of female paratype (5) and male holotype (6) under UV light..." and "...tergites of female paratype (7) and male holotype (8) and under UV light...", were figure caption errors, and the sexes should be switched.

(2) Page 20 (right column): "...29°12'91"N 97°57'73"E...", was deviated from reality, and the correct coordinates should be "29°06'39.0"N 97°58'26.0"E (29.11083°N, 97.97389°E)". The error was due to the use of an online coordinate format converter (in certain cases, specimen coordinates provided by the collector were in decimal format); no errors for the map because it used the original decimal format (Tang et al., 2023: fig. 86). Similar errors of Yunnan *Scorpiops* may appear in Tang (2022d, 2022e), and readers may refer to Tang (2024b) where all coordinates are corrected. All coordinates in subsequent papers (start from Tang (2023)) were and will be corroborated in Google Maps.

5. Tang (2023):

(1) Page 42: "Figures 196–199. *Scorpiops jendeki*, male (97,

98) and female (99, 100) pectines.”, was a figure caption error, which should be “(196, 198)” and “(197, 199)” respectively.

(2) Page 43, fig. 201, the dot color was not separated for *S. zhangshuyuani* and *S. sp.* (Jinghong) in the scatterplot. To clarify, the pink dot clustered with *S. vachoni* represents *S. sp.* (Jinghong).

6. Tang et al. (2024a):

(1) Page 4 (left column): “...DNA sequencing and phylogenetic tree reconstruction. *This part was performed by the third and fourth authors...*”, was an uncorrected text, which should be “*fifth*” and “*third*” respectively. The sequence of coauthors was rearranged during the final review.

(2) Page 19 (left column): “...*In fact, the two species can be easily discriminated by character 6 alone...*”, was an uncorrected number, which should be “13”. The sequence of preceding characters was rearranged during the writing.

In addition, there was a print error for Tang et al. (2024a: fig. 130) in the caption where the symbols were not shown: “...*topotypes examined in this study (white dots)*; “*M. c. intermedius*” *studied in previous Chinese papers (white squares)*...”.

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